

Near-field microwave focusing evaluation of dielectric lens antenna for human body model

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ABSTRACT

Various small focus spot applicators are being investigated for hyperthermia therapy, which requires microwave concentration to heat tumors in the human body. Dielectric lens antenna is frequency independent and has strong focusing capability to achieve a very small focusing spot. In this paper, lenses with diameters of 30, 50 and 70 cm were designed to evaluate the size of the focal spot in the human body model. The electromagnetic simulator, FEKO was used to generate rays and near-field focusing data of dielectric lenses at a frequency of 2.45 GHz. The simulated focal spot sizes agreed well with the theoretical values. An analytical investigation into the power at the focal spot was conducted using the proposed power relations of the focused lens novel equation. The theoretical propagation loss is used to represent the power density degradation at the focal spot caused by microwave absorption by the human body. The simulation results of the focused lens in the human body indicated that the 30 cm lens achieved a larger focal spot with a greater focusing power, 0.714 mW compared to the 70 cm lens, which achieved a smaller focal spot but a lower focusing power, which was 0.393 mW.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The use of concentrated microwave radiation to heat tumors has attracted the interest of researchers in employing external microwave applicators on human biological tissues for medical therapy, known as hyperthermia [1], [2]. External microwave hyperthermia is a noninvasive therapy in which the applicator is placed externally near to the targeted tumor [3]. Considering tumors have slower rates of temperature cooling due to restricted blood flow [4], the microwave radiation aims to deliver the power to the tumors to achieve sufficient tumor damage without harming the surrounding healthy tissues. The near-field focused antenna is greatly known for its capability to concentrate radiated electromagnetic (EM) waves to a small focusing spot [5], which is useful for medical treatments that need high-power density at a focal point close to the antenna aperture.

In the case of focused hyperthermia applicator, several types of antennas [6]-[12] were designed to localize microwave power in human biological tissues. Initially, the adaptive phased array hyperthermia system was designed [13] to produce the required field intensity at the tumor and eliminate unintended hot spots. Multiple antennas phased array systems with rigid antenna components were also developed [14], [15] and

have been used in clinical trials to treat head and neck targets [16]. Although these applicators provide advanced energy deposition control, system complexity, as well as large dimensions and weight, must be addressed in a clinical setting. In addition, more research was conducted to obtain small focusing spot to ensure localization of microwave power to the targeted tumor tissue. A near-field focused folded transmit array antenna [17] with a diameter of $D=54$ cm was positioned 40 cm in front of human leg tissues for medical applications. The focusing spot had a radius of 7.5 cm at -3dB spot area. Another 2.4 GHz near-field 4×4 microstrip focused array antenna for medical applications was also presented [18]. According to the simulation, a -3dB spot was enclosed in a region of approximately 10 cm, that has been mentioned to be adequate for focusing the EM power in small areas of biological tissues for clinical application. However, the operating frequency band of array antenna was limited. A 19 cm cylindrical left-handed metamaterial (LHM) lens to heat superficial tumor at 2.45 GHz was proposed [19]. Depending on the distance between two microwave sources, the achieved focused resolution ranged from 0.7 to 2.04 cm. Nonetheless, the metamaterial-based antennas have certain limitations, such as the fact that it only operates in a restricted frequency range and is difficult to manufacture.

The novelty of this paper is that it evaluates the near-field focusing of the fundamental dielectric lens antenna that concentrates microwave into the human body model relative to the antenna diameter. Although the proposed focused lens design is unable to represent real condition of the hyperthermia therapy applicator, it is somehow useful to investigate the condition of power concentration and the focal spot size inside the human body model which provides significant information for designing hyperthermia therapy applicators in the future.

The paper is organized as shown in; section 2 introduces the fundamental design concept of the focused dielectric lens antenna, theoretical concept of the followings; focal spot size, power relations of the lens and power degradation in the lossy material. The simulation parameters of the focused dielectric lens are then provided in section 3. In Section 4, the simulations results of the electric power concentration at the focus spot are presented. Section 5 concludes the findings obtained from the analysis in the paper.

2. FOCUSED DIELECTRIC LENS ANTENNA DESIGN

The equations to design the lens shapes are explained. The lenses were designed for the free space and the human body model. The lens shaping accuracy was validated using the ray tracing method based on ray launching-geometrical optics (RL-GO).

2.1. Fundamental of the dual focused lens antenna

In the first convex lens, the distance from the feed to the first hyperbolic lens surface, S_1 is expressed by r_1 . Flat surface of the first convex lens is S_2 while its central thickness is T_1 . Another hyperbolic surface for the second convex lens is indicated by S_4 . The ray path from S_4 to the Focus 2 is represented by r_2 . The flat surface for second convex lens is S_3 and its central thickness is T_2 . Around the z-axis, the lens is rotated symmetrically, and the radial direction of the lens corresponds to the y-axis as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Dual focused lens structure

The feed was set at the coordinates of (0,0). The hyperbolic surfaces of lens 1 ($i=1$) and lens 2 ($i=2$) were determined by (1) [20]. The focal length is defined by F and the refractive index is defined by n .

$$r_i = \frac{(n-1)F_i}{n \cos \theta_{i-1}} \quad (1)$$

The ray path, r begins at the feed point and ends at the Focus 2 point. The lens thickness, T_i [20] is given by (2) with D_L denoting the lens diameter.

$$T_i = \frac{1}{n+1} \left(\sqrt{F_i^2 + \frac{(n+1)D_L^2}{4(n-1)}} - F_i \right) \tag{2}$$

The feed emits a spherical wave at (0,0) coordinates, transforms to a plane wave when passing through the converging lens, and then returns to a spherical wave at Focus 2.

2.2. Ray tracing of the focused dielectric lens antenna in the free space

Lens antenna shaping accuracy is validated using the ray launching-geometrical optics (RL-GO) solver of the FEKO simulator. The rays are shown in Figure 2. Ray tracing result shows that the lens shape was correctly designed as the focal length F_1 equals F_2 . The simulation parameters of the ray analysis in Figure 2 are shown in Table 1.

Figure 2. Ray analysis of focused dielectric lens $D_L=30$ cm

Table 1. Focused dielectric lens antenna configuration in free space

Parameter	Value
Refractive Index (n)	3
Lens Diameter (D_L)	30 cm
Focal Length ($F_1 = F_2$)	13 cm
Lens Thickness ($T_1 = T_2$)	2.97 cm

2.3. Focused dielectric lens antenna to focus inside the human body model

Focused lens structure for human body model is shown in Figure 3. The human body part is shown by the area with refractive index n_2 ($n_2 > n_1$). The focus point is indicated by focus 2.

Figure 3. Focused lens structure for human body model

The concave lens shape to focus EM waves in the human body equivalent tissue model was designed by modifying (1) into (3):

$$r_m = \frac{F_2(n_2 - n)}{(n_2 - n \cos \theta_m)} \tag{3}$$

The refractive index of the human body, n_2 takes the value of $n_2 = \sqrt{\langle \varepsilon_r \rangle}$, where ε_r is defined as (4).

$$\langle \varepsilon_r \rangle = \varepsilon_r - j \frac{\sigma}{\omega \varepsilon_0} = \varepsilon_r - j60\lambda_0\sigma \quad (4)$$

In the case of actual human tissues, conductivity ranges from $0.1 < \sigma < 2$ [21]. In most cases, $\sigma < 0.5$ is dominant. In this paper, $\sigma = 0.5$ was applied to (4). Therefore, $\langle \varepsilon_r \rangle = 52.7 - j3.6$. For the convenience of calculation, ε_r takes the value of 52.7 while σ can be neglected. Ray, r of the convex lens was designed by using (1) and T_1 of the convex lens was determined using (2). Then, convex and concave lenses were combined using (5).

$$r \cdot \sin \theta = r_m \cdot \sin \theta_m = \frac{D_L}{2} \quad (5)$$

As the thickness of concave lens, T_2 was set to a predetermined value, t was calculated and can be obtained using (6).

$$t = F_2 - \cos \theta_m \cdot r_m \quad (6)$$

2.4. Ray tracing of the the focused dielectric lens antenna for the human body model

The focused dielectric lens antenna for the human body model was analysed using RL-GO solver. The simulation involved three different mediums: free space, lens and human body of refractive index, $n_1=1$, $n=3$ and $n_2=7.26$, respectively. The produced rays as in Figure 4 clearly verified that the focused dielectric lens antenna concept for human body was designed according to the derived equations. The characteristics of the focused dielectric lens antenna for the human body are shown in Table 2.

Figure 4. Ray analysis of focused dielectric lens antenna for the human body model

Table 2. Focused dielectric lens antenna configuration for the human body

Parameter	Value
Refractive Index (n)	3
Lens Diameter (D_L)	30 cm
Focal Length (F_1)	13 cm
Focal Length (F_2)	26.1 cm
Lens Thickness (T_1)	2.97 cm
Lens Thickness (T_2)	1 cm

2.5. Theoretical focal spot size

Focusing antenna concentrates microwave energy at a point in front of the lens in a small spot. As a result, energy is focused in one direction and energy transmission in other directions are avoided [22]. Theoretical focal spot size, S_T of lens antenna [23] can be calculated using (7). The wavelength in a medium is indicated by λ_g . While, F_{Total} equals to the summation of the focal length and half of the converging lens' thickness.

$$S_T = \frac{1.22 F_{Total} \lambda_g}{D_L} \quad (7)$$

According to the expression d in Figure 5, its relation to the spot size is described by (8):

$$d = 2S_T \tag{8}$$

Figure 5. Focal spot size parameters of focused lens antenna

2.6. Power relations of the focused dielectric lens

Equations that express power relations of the lens were derived according to the diagram shown in Figure 6. The captured power inside the cone area of \$\theta_L\$ (rad), \$P_C\$ is expressed by (9) with \$A_C\$ as the captured area and the transmitted power of the feed dipole antenna is represented by \$P_T\$.

$$P_C = \frac{A_C}{4\pi r^2} P_T \tag{9}$$

The captured area, \$A_C\$ of the lens area can be calculated by (10).

$$A_C = \pi \theta_L^2 r^2 \tag{10}$$

Angle, \$\theta_L\$ (rad) is calculated by (11).

$$\theta_L = \tan^{-1} \frac{(DL/2)}{F+t} [rad] \tag{11}$$

Then, \$P_C\$ is expressed by (12).

$$P_C = \frac{\theta_L^2}{4} P_T \tag{12}$$

The following expressions (13)-(15) were considered to calculate the transmission coefficient, \$T_1\$ and \$T_2\$ and the power transmitted by lens antenna, \$P_L\$.

$$T_1 = \frac{4n_1n_2}{(n_1+n_2)^2} \tag{13}$$

$$T_2 = \frac{4n_2n_3}{(n_2+n_3)^2} \tag{14}$$

$$P_L = P_C T_1 T_2 = \frac{\theta_L^2}{4} P_T T_1 T_2 \tag{15}$$

The area of the focal spot, \$A_S\$ is indicated by (16) with \$S\$ is the diameter of the focal spot size. The power, \$P_{-3}\$ at -3dB power density, \$W_{-3}\$ is given by (17).

$$A_S = \pi \left(\frac{S}{2}\right)^2 \tag{16}$$

$$P_{-3} = A_S W_{-3} \tag{17}$$

Then, the concentrated power at the focal spot, \$P_S\$ is given by (18).

$$P_S = 1.5P_{-3} \tag{18}$$

The diagram in Figure 6 describes the focal spot power, P_s , the outside power that surrounded the spot area, P_o and the diffracted power, P_D as the three components of the lens antenna power, P_L . P_D is produced by multiple reflections inside the lens.

Figure 6. Power transmission through lens

2.7. Power degradation in the lossy material

In EM waves propagation, electric field (E-field) in the lossy material is expressed as follows (19). Where σ indicates the conductivity of the material and α is the attenuation constant (20) in nepers per meter (Np/m). The EM waves travelling distance is denoted by z which is in meter (m).

$$E(z) = E_o e^{-\alpha z} \tag{19}$$

$$\alpha = \omega \sqrt{\frac{\mu_o \epsilon_o \epsilon_r}{2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\sigma}{\omega \epsilon_o \epsilon_r}\right)^2} - 1 \right]} \tag{20}$$

In addition, the propagation loss, P_{Loss} in the lossy material given by (21) was used to estimate the power degradation within the human body model when EM waves is focused by the lens.

$$P_{Loss}(dB) = 20 \log e^{-\alpha z} = - 8.686 \alpha z \tag{21}$$

3. SIMULATION BY THE ELECTROMAGNETIC SIMULATOR

The simulation of the focused lens design in the free space and for the human body model were investigated using lenses with diameters, D_L of 30, 50, and 70 cm at 2.45 GHz. The simulation by the electromagnetic simulator, FEKO were performed to interpolate the focal spot sizes ranging from 30 to 70 cm. The simulation parameters are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Simulation parameters for the focused dielectric lens antenna

Item	Parameter	Value		
EM Simulator Solver	-	FEKO 2019, MoM/ FEM Hybrid		
Frequency (f)	-	2.45 GHz		
Wavelength (λ_o)	-	12.24 cm		
Feed Antenna (Half- λ Dipole)	Length	5.836 cm		
	Wire Radius	0.01224 cm		
	Transmit Power (P_T)	0.014 W [$R_m=73 \Omega, V= 1V$]		
Lens 1 (Lens 2 in Free Space)	Refractive Index (n)	3		
	Diameter (D_L)	30 cm	50 cm	70 cm
	Focal Length ($F_1= F_2$)	13 cm	15 cm	20 cm
	Wavelength (λ)	12.24 cm		
Lens 2 for Human Body	Refractive Index (n)	3		
	Diameter (D_L)	30 cm	50 cm	70 cm
	Focal Length (F_1)	13 cm	15 cm	20 cm
	Focal Length (F_2)	26.1 cm	40.8 cm	56.8 cm
Human Body	Permittivity (ϵ_r)	52.7		
	Conductivity (σ)	0 (Spot size calculation) 0, 0.5, 1.0 & 1.95 (Power degradation)		
	Wavelength (λ_p)	1.69 cm		

Simulation models for investigating the focal spot size using focused lens Figure 7. The simulation model of the focused lens in the free space is shown in Figure 7(a), whereas Figure 7(b) depicts the simulation model of a human body. Close proximity configuration can improve microwave energy coupling and localization to the tissue. Therefore, the simulation for the human body condition is regarded as the simulation purpose only and does not portray the real human body condition because the initial simulation data needs to be collected and analyzed.

Figure 7. Simulation models for investigating the focal spot size using focused lens; (a) focused lens in the free space and (b) focused lens for the human body model

Simulated performance of the feed antenna Figure 8. The simulation model of the focused dielectric lens antenna in the free space was used to verify the lens focusing concept while, the focused dielectric lens antenna for the human body was used to investigate the focal spot size and electric power distributions in a human body model. Half-wavelength dipole antenna was used as the feed antenna due to its simplicity. The simulated performance of the feed antenna in terms of radiation pattern and normalized reflection coefficient, S_{11} are illustrated in Figures 8(a) and 8(b), respectively. The radiation pattern shows that the power was distributed omni-directionally over a radiation sphere.

Figure 8. Simulated performance of the feed antenna based on (a) radiation pattern and (b) S_{11}

4. ELECTRIC POWER CONCENTRATION AT THE FOCUS SPOT

In order to ensure the focusing ability of the focused lens, focusing analysis at the focus spot in the free space is first presented in terms of the focal spot size evaluation. Then, the power concentration at the focus spot is described. The same approach is applied to evaluate the focusing performance inside the human body model.

4.1. Focusing of power in the free space

The results of the free space focusing conditions are shown in Table 4. Power is concentrated around $Z=F_2$ in the Y-Z plane and power is distributed along the Z axis. The power concentration spot becomes small with a large lens diameter. The spot sizes at -3dB are represented by the power distributions in the X-Y plane.

Table 4. Simulated power density distribution in the free space

Simulated near-fied focusing in the free space for $D_L=30, 50$ and 70 cm in terms of as shown in Figure 9. The near-field focusing effects in the free space in terms of the focal spot size and the power densities are shown in Figures 9(a) and (b), respectively. The theoretical spot size, S_T of (7) are compared to the simulated focal spot size, S_{-3dB} in Figure 9(a). Although S_{-3dB} values are larger than S_T , the trend of both S_{-3dB} and S_T values shows good agreement for all cases of $D_L=30, 50$ and 70 cm.

However, evaluation of the focal spot size in the free space is not significant in this study; nonetheless, it demonstrates that the approach can be utilized to validate the focal spot size in the human body model. The simulated power density values at the focal spot for $D_L=30, 50$ and 70 cm are shown in Figure 9(b). The increase in power density is approximately proportional to the increment of the lens antenna diameter, D_L .

Figure 9. Simulated near-fied focusing in the free space for $D_L=30, 50$ and 70 cm in terms of (a) focal spot size and (b) power densities

4.2. Power at the focus spot in the free space

In order to evaluate the power concentration at the focus spot that is produced by the focused dielectric lens antenna, calculations were performed according to (9)-(18). Following that, the calculated power values are summarized in Table 5. The transmit power source, P_T by the feed antenna was calculated using (22).

$$P_T = \frac{V^2}{R} = \frac{1^2}{73} \text{ (W)} \tag{22}$$

Table 5. Power relations in the free space

D_L (cm)	P_T (W)	θ_L (rad)	P_C (mW)	T_1T_2	P_L (mW)	W_{-3} (mW/cm ²)	A_S (cm ²)	P_{-3} (mW)	P_S (mW)
30	0.014	0.754	1.99	0.56	1.12	0.00359	76.05	0.273	0.409
50	0.014	0.876	2.69	0.56	1.51	0.00507	60.27	0.306	0.458
70	0.014	0.890	2.77	0.56	1.56	0.00779	45.84	0.357	0.536

The estimated values of P_S which is $P_S=P_L/3$ denotes that $P_D=P_O=P_S$. As described previously in section 2.6, P_L is composed of P_S , P_O and P_D . Power relation between P_L and power at focal spot, P_S is shown in Figure 10 which is reduced to only one third of the power that is produced by the focused dielectric lens antenna.

Figure 10. Power relations in the free space

4.3. Focusing of power inside the human body model

In the focused hyperthermia therapy, radiation deposition into the human biological tissues is preferred to be in minimum spot size which indicates that only the area at the focal point will be heated rather than the surrounding areas. The simulated power densities at the focal spot within the human body model are shown in Table 6. Data at $\sigma=0$ were used to analyse the spot sizes. As the conductivity inside the human body model increased, power density at the focal point decreased. Moreover, the focal spot size decreased with increasing lens diameter. As shown in Table 6, power density degradation was significantly greater at $\sigma=1.0$ for $D_L=50$ cm.

Simulated near-field focusing inside the human body for $D_L=30, 50$ and 70 cm in terms of as shown in Figure 11. The near-field focusing effects inside the human body in terms of the focal spot size and the power densities are shown in Figure 11(a) and (b), respectively. The spot sizes obtained from the simulations in the X-Y plane at $Z=F_2$ are plotted in Figure 11(a). The S_T and S_{-3dB} in the human body matched extremely well. The size of the focal spots in the human body model appeared to be smaller due to the higher relative permittivity, ϵ_r of the human body [24] compared to the free space. As shown in Figure 11(b), the simulated power densities at the focal spot for $\sigma=0$ increased as D_L increased.

4.4. Power at the focus spot inside the human body model

Subsequently, the total power concentrated at the spot area in the human body model was calculated. The calculated values using (9)-(18) were based on the calculation of the free space condition. The calculated values are summarized in Table 7.

As described in Figure 12, power that was produced by the lens antenna, P_L was higher in $D_L=70$ cm as compared to $D_L=30$ cm. However, the P_S of $D_L=70$ cm was lower than the P_S of $D_L=30$ cm. Referring to Table 7, $P_S= P_L/2$ for $D_L=30$ cm. Meanwhile, $P_S=P_L/4$ for $D_L=70$ cm. The lower value of P_S for $D_L=70$ cm is due to the lower P_{-3} value in which, according to (17), having a smaller focal spot area, A_S has resulted in a lower P_{-3} value. This is true in the case of $D_L=70$ cm because a smaller focal spot size was achieved by $D_L=70$ cm as compared to $D_L=30$ cm. This is also supported by the slight variation in -3 dB power density, W_{-3} between $D_L=30, 50$ and 70 cm. In addition, the P_O of $D_L=70$ cm was greater than the P_O of $D_L=30$ cm.

At 2.45 GHz, a human body equivalent tissue model with relative permittivity of 52.7 and conductivity of 1.95 was referred [25] to investigate power density at the focal spot that is influenced by the conductivity of the human body. A lens of $D_L=50$ cm was used in the simulation with human body conductivity values of 0, 0.5, 1.0 and 1.95. Table 8 displays the variation in power densities as a function of conductivity and the P_{Loss} values calculated. The P_{Loss} were calculated using (21) with the microwave traveling distance, $z=40.8$ cm or 0.408 m that equals to F_2 in the human body model. It was demonstrated that, considering the impact of conductivity in the human body, the obtained P_{Loss} values may be utilized to determine the power density degradations at the focusing spot.

Table 6. Simulated power density distribution inside the human body

Figure 11. Simulated near-fied focusing inside the human body for $D_L=30, 50$ and 70 cm in terms of (a) focal spot size and (b) power densities of $\sigma=0$

Table 7. Power relations in the human body model

D_L (cm)	P_T (W)	θ_L (rad)	P_C (mW)	$T_1 T_2$	P_L (mW)	W_{-3} (mW/cm ²)	A_S (cm ²)	P_{-3} (mW)	P_S (mW)
30	0.014	0.754	1.99	0.62	1.24	0.196	2.43	0.476	0.714
50	0.014	0.876	2.69	0.62	1.67	0.210	1.86	0.390	0.585
70	0.014	0.890	2.77	0.62	1.73	0.228	1.15	0.262	0.393

Figure 12. Power relation in the human body model

Table 8. Variation in power densities and the estimation of power degradations of $D_L=50$ cm

ϵ_r	σ	α	Power Density (dBW/m ²)	Normalized Power Density (dBW/m ²)	P_{Loss} (dB) *(21)
52.7	0	0	5.51	0	0
	0.5	13	- 36.9	- 42.41	- 46.07
	1.0	26	- 78.6	- 84.11	- 92.14
	1.95	50	- 147.0	- 152.51	- 177.19

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the focusing ability of the dielectric lens antenna to achieve a small spot size in the human body model were verified through the construction of lenses with diameters of 30, 50 and 70 cm at 2.45 GHz. The simulation results shows that the power density at the focal spot were reduced due to the increased conductivity of the human body model. In addition, the power density degradation at the focal spot in the human body model due to the conductivity can be estimated using the P_{Loss} equation. Through the theoretical analysis of power estimation at the focal spot, it was shown that the focused dielectric lens antenna of $D_L = 30$ cm achieved higher focusing power compared to the $D_L=0$ cm. Despite the fact that the lenses in this study were not tested in the experiment due to their large diameter, the simulation results demonstrated that the proposed theoretical equations are valid. The findings in this paper contributed to an understanding of the approach to achieve a small focal spot size in the human body and the power degradation condition, which could be used as a guide for designing, fabricating, and testing smaller and thinner focused dielectric lens antenna for hyperthermia therapy in the near future.

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